

PREPARE cluster activities

CO-VERSATILE Project:

Prepare Europe for future disruptions.

EU's CO-VERSATILE project reached a new milestone in facilitating collaboration between the European manufacturing market players. Novel platform – the Digital Technopole – will lift Europe's preparedness to counteract future disruptions to new heights.

Check out the Digital Technopole Digital Technopole - Home (co-versatile.eu) and read the announcement. Learn more about the platform and about the project results recently shared at SME Resilience Days | CO-VERSATILE

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/CoVersatile>

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/co-versatile/>

Web: [Europe's manufacturing rapid responsiveness for vital medical equipment | CO-VERSATILE](#)

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